

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

GEORGIAN POLITICAL THEOLOGY AT THE CROSSROADS OF CHRISTIAN PHILOSOPHY AND THE ENLIGHTENMENT (“RUIS-URBNISI LEGAL DECREE” AND “KALMASOBA” BY IOANE BATONISHVILI)

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ABSTRACT

The following article portrayed the fundamental principles of Georgian political thought, which historically represented a synthesis of Christian teachings and philosophical reasoning.

Georgia is a country that has not waged a war of conquest throughout its 2,000-year history of Christianity, and since the origins of philosophical thought are directly connected to the idea of sovereignty, the work unveils those type of Georgian political ideas that always been formed on the basis of Christian beliefs, was taking the form of Christian Philosophy, and ultimately developed into Georgian Political Theology.

To illustrate this, the paper draws on two key documents: “*Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree*” – the first medieval text of original Georgian canonical writing (11th Century), and “*Kalmasoba*” by the nobleman Ioane Batonishvili – the first Georgian text with characteristics of the Enlightenment era (1813-1828). In the first case, the text is the chronotype of Orthodox Church’s canonry, while in the second case, a work of the encyclopedic genre that conveys knowledge across every field of the history of intellectual thought.

Keywords: Political Theology, Christian Philosophy, Georgian Philosophy, Medieval Philosophy, Enlightenment.

Problem Statement and Recent Studies and Publications

In medieval Georgia, Christian philosophical ideas were revealed not only through the translation of theological and dialectical treatises, but also in hagiographic, biographical, metaphrastic, and fictional literature.

Since the Georgian monarchs considered themselves descendants of the Biblical King David (It should be noted that more than bloodline posterity they had a self-aware sense of spiritual chritotony), this was on of the defining elements of their political vision, which carried a deep significant theological basis, hence Georgian cultural identity expresses the ideology of National Messianism. This type of approach furthermore develops into Political Anthropology where the “Body” of the the nation has the “Mind”, which, like the Old Testament Israel, is capable to see God.

It must be fairly mentioned that this perception is reinforced by the ancient Church traditions claiming Georgia’s allotment to Mother of God, founded Apostolic Church by the disciples and the presence of Orthodox relics in the country, such as The Robe of The Christ, The Robe of the Most Holy Mother of God, The Mantle of The Prophet Elijah, The Bones of The Apostles, etc. Thus, the image of the sovereign as the executor of Divine governance is formed, whilst the architectonics of medieval texts clearly reveals the tendency to interpret ideas in context of The Creation and The Eschatology (The Georgian rule and terms of Coronation also validates that).

The fundamental influence of the Christian religion and philosophical ideas on the political life of Georgia has become a subject of research for modern Georgian scholars. Based on examination of the historical context and existing challenges, the role of the legal regulation of state and enlightenment as an opportunity for modern society to acquire knowledge, finally becomes obvious in the ongoing process of establishing Political Theology as an act of manifestation of centuries-long basement of statehood in faith and knowledge.

Like so, among recent Georgian studies on Christian philosophy and Political Theology, the following should be highlighted:

Metropolitan Grigoli (Berbichashvili). *Iona Khelashvili’s Metaphysical Conception*. Ed. Iremadze T., Zakaradze L., Jeck. U. R. Hchneider H. Tbilisi, 2017.

Iremadze T. *Medieval Georgian Philosophy. A Systematic Outline to Understand its Specifics*. Ed. Zakaradze L., Khuroshvili G. Tbilisi, 2019.

Iremadze T. *Early Modern Georgian Philosophy. A Systematic Outline to Understand its Specifics*. Ed. Gogatishvili M., Zakaradze L., Khuroshvili G., Tbilisi, 2020.

Jeck. U. R. Vakhtang Gorgasali – Chrsitian and Philosopher King. Tr. By Khuroshvili G. Ed. Metropolitan Grigoli (Berbichashvili), Zakaradze L., Iremadze T. Tbilisi, 2019.

Khuroshvili G. *Political Theology in Medieval Georgia*. Ed. Iremadze T. Tbilisi, 2022.

Kopaleishvili N. St. Ketevan. Martyred Monarch's Image in the Georgian Thought. Ed. Iremadze T. Tbilisi, 2022.

Philosophy and Theology in Medieval Georgia. Ed. Iremadze T. Tbilisi, 2016.

Early Modern Georgian Philosophy and its Major Representatives. Ed. Iremadze T. Tbilisi, 2014.

Gogatishvili M. Ideological and political paradigms of the medieval Georgian state. 2020. In: Petritsi Online Portal – <http://petritsiportal.ge/ka/article/31>

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Zakaradze L. New Perspectives of Georgian Philosophy in the Light of Intercultural Thought. In: European Scientific Journal. Vol. 2. 2013.

Zakaradze L. The Most Important Monument of Medieval Georgian Legal Thinking: „The Great Canon Law”. In: Materialien zur. Vol. 38. 2012.

Purpose of the Article

The present publication in one hand, is an attempt to, based on a structural and ideological examination, reveal previously unexplored aspects of Georgian Political Theology through a review of Georgian legal and Enlightenment era's type of texts, on the other hand, to raise awareness of Georgian Christian Philosophical culture, both among readers interested in these topics and within European academic organisations.

Main Material

Primarily, it should be noted that Political Philosophy in Georgia is Christocentric.

In an Orthodox state, society, unlike in the Roman Empire, is free from: *sacrilegium*, or the crime against faith, *crima laesae majestatis*, or the crime against the sovereignty and *ars magica*, from prosecution for crimes involving magical practices. Since the ruler himself seeks sovereignty to fulfill Divine will, therefore true monarchy, from the very beginning, is eschatological where *παρουσία*, or the salvation of souls, is central.

In this sense, as the allure of an earthly kingdom is the humanity's greatest temptation, the medieval Georgian monarch rules *sub specie aeternitatis* – from the perspective of eternity and his (as well as God's) only opposing force is not a political rival but the devil and ones who abode in apostasy.

In general, for future researchers interested in this topic, it should also be said that Georgian Political Theology, like the Old Testament Prophecies, must be explained in backwards, in reverse. Meaning the fact that an event occurs in the world not because it was predicted that way, but, on the contrary – because this or that event took its place, it was precisely for this reason that it was Prophesied centuries ago. It is noteworthy that in the First book of Samuel we read how the Israelites ask the Prophet Samuel to appoint a human king for them (i.e., they no longer want Divine rule). The gathered people say: “Now make us a king to judge us like all the nations” (1 Samuel 8:5), to which the Lord responds to the Prophet who is saddened by their request: “Hearken unto the voice of the people in all that they say unto thee: for they have not rejected thee, but they have rejected me, that I should not reign over

them” (1 Samuel 8:7). We must understand Georgian Political Theology from this perspective. Because, unlike the Israelites, Georgian society desired not a human king, but for God Himself (not a creation, but uncreated) to reign. This revives the diptych of the prelapsarian world: “Man-God” and when Saul, the first anointed king who rejected God, was replaced by the God bearing David, who obeyed the Lord, the Georgian monarchs consider themselves spiritual descendants of him. This self-consciousness of sovereignty, in above-mentioned diptych, presents the ruler as the image and after likeness of God (not just an image and likeness of himself or his royal authority) and a new triptych is created: “Man-King-God,” because in the Pauline Epistle to the Romans it says: “Let every soul be subject unto the higher powers. For there is no power but of God: the powers that be are ordained of God” (Romans 13:1). This is the basis of Georgian Political Theology, as in Georgia, the king is a human, but he is also the image and likeness of God and thus, the state is under the Divine governance and under the rule of the Lord as *Παντοκράτωρ*.

All of this fundamentally distinguishes Georgian thought from other cultures and makes it unique compared to other political worldviews, and it can be safely said that *pluralis majestatis* in Georgian Political Theology can only be attributed to One God.

To form a comprehensive understanding of the matter, it is also of utmost importance to note that Georgian state ideology is formed on the basis of a complete understanding of the Eucharistic mystery. Since the Eucharist (*εὐχαριστία*), or making the Sacrament for Communion, as the “Thanksgiving” is an essential and vital part of the Divine Liturgy (*λεειτουργία*), or “Public Service”, during which bread and wine becoming The Body and The Blood of The Lord, and it begins with the proskomide (*προσκομιδή*), or the “Oblation” of that bread and wine by the people themselves, whose names are mentioned one by one during the preparation for the Sacrament. This includes the context revealed in Jerusalem during the Last Supper. Specifically, at the establishment of the Eucharistic tradition, when the Savior, surrounded by the twelve apostles, said: “This do in remembrance of me” (Luke 22:19) and later: “Verily, verily, I say unto you, that one of you shall betray me” (John 13:21). Accordingly, the Divine Liturgy which is divided into two parts: the service of the Catechumens (at which every non baptized people can attend) and the service of Righteous (at which the Sacrament of Communion is prepared and only baptized Christians are able to be part of), parallels the separation of the eleven righteous apostles from the one apostate, into whom the devil entered and who turns out to be Judas of Iscariot.

As mentioned earlier, this article draws upon the first Georgian legal document, the “Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree” and the first Georgian Enlightenment era's type of text, “*Kalmasoba*” written by Ioane Batonishvili.

In one case, the Church council convened by King David IV the Builder in Ruis-Urbnisi proposes a canon which regulates and governs the sanctity and functioning of the Church (where the Eucharistic tradition takes its place) and small-scale Church – e.i., family (whose

members, as parishioners, are expected to offer bread and wine to the Church). In the second case, the protagonist of the text, Protodeacon Iona Khelashvili, begins a journey to replenish the supply of bread and wine for the Monastery, as to say, he is going for “*Kalmasoba*” (medieval Georgian technical term, meaning going outside of the Monastery to collect and replenish the supply of bread and wine) and during his travels, he preaches and spreads knowledge about all branches of science among ordinary people of country.

This is the pattern of Georgian Political Theology that is formed at the intersection of Christian Philosophy and idea of Enlightenment. And for this reason, the Georgian rite of Coronation, which anoints the royal candidate who is a guarantor of the ecclesiastical and enlightened nature of society, involves key procedure – the placement of royal regalia (Crown, Scepter, Sakkos and Mantle) on the Paten, on which obliterated bread will be carved in the name of its each offerer and parishioner, and then placed on the Holy Table and gently intinctioned in a Chalice filled with consecrated wine, where they transform into The Body and The Blood of The Savior.

Thus, the synthesis of Georgian political thought and Enlightenment ideas reaches its highest expression in Christian Philosophy.

“Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree”

It is worth mentioning that the extremely difficult political legacy and challenges which King David IV the Builder (1089-1125) was facing could only be cured by establishing appropriate order to heal the existing spiritual ulcer and wounds of both the country and the Church.

The country, devastated by the constant invasions of Seljuk Turks, the massacred and exiled population, the arbitrariness of secular and clerical hierarchs, the rebelled feudal class and the such danger of ethnical and moral degeneration of society, needless to say, required a type of healing activity that not only regulated daily norms of life, but also firmly defined principles of restoring spiritual condition of citizenry.

The historian, who considers the managing of the “*Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree*” as the foundation of the restorative activities initiated by King David, when describing his spiritual condition states: “Then the king, with the eye of his mind and kindness of his heart, willingly supervise this to be done, for it would please God and in return would be a remarkable benefit” [2. 326]. And, regarding his enthronement, he continues: “He was sixteen years of age at the time [...] his father himself crowned him king, and, truthfully speaking, it was the Heavenly Father who chose David, His servant, and anointed him, for the Hand of The Lord was with him, and His Arms strengthened him” [2. 324].

The “Decree” consists of three parts: preface, section of the laws (19 canons altogether), and a chronicle and festal praise of King David and Georgian historical figures. As the works of the Holy Fathers shows, beyond the horizon of human words lies the mysterious side of God’s providence. For this reason, the preface of “*Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree*” begins with a narra-

tive of the Hexameron (The six days of Biblical Creation) and then lists the punishments inflicted by the Lord upon the world:

- After Adam and Eve took the forbidden fruit from the Tree of Knowledge of Good and Evil, they were expelled from The Paradise.

- Killing his brother Abel the righteous by Cain led to the second wrath of God upon the world.

- Annihilate of the humanity by the Great Flood, and the survival of Noah the righteous and his family only through the construction of the Ark.

- The confusion of tongues resulting from the Construction of the Tower of Babel.

- Raining sulfur and fire on Sodom and Gomorrah and demolishing everything upon because of their unimaginable sickness of filth and corresponding behaviors.

- Ten plagues sent upon the Pharaoh and Egyptians for enslaving Israelites.

Since “non of the abovelisted punishments [...] were able to completely heal human nature [...] for this reason The Wisdom and The Power and The One Essence with The Father – The Word of God who was in the beginning and eternaly was with God and was God [...] came to the earth for our souls and Became Flesh, so that with alike humanly nature purify ours” [3. 544].

Notably, before announcing the laws, the “*Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree*” outlines all the existing legal acts of Christianity, such as the Law of Moses, The Seven Ecumenical Councils, Local Councils of Autocephalous Churches, and Individual canons of the Holy Fathers.

The fact that for the Georgian monarch the state is metaphysical, - in order for the Church, as a Divine institution, to be able to maintain the balance of the spiritual and the physical, it needs an external legal norm of a coercive nature, which, simultaneously from the very beginning, will contribute to the unified healing process of the human conscience and physical body. In addition, in the context of National Messianism, where the anointed king is the Image and Likeness of God, he is intended to become the guarantor of humans *Theosis* and return to Paradise. Because the operational purpose of the Ecumenical or Local Church Councils is the same: to eliminate spiritual distortions and illnesses, continuation of the Salvific activity of The Incarnate Savior.

The Church Council of Ruis-Urbnisi held no earlier than 1103, proposed a decree consisting of 19 laws. Among these:

- 11 laws concern the work of the clergy (Unworthy bishops are excommunicated; Age restrictions for different hierarchical ranks are established; the use of “The Great Echulogian” mandated by St. George the Hagiorite; Banning of simony; Prohibition of personal usage of church and monastery supplies and goods; Restriction of number of Clergy in a single monastery; Banning of buying and trading at Church’s yard; The necessity of knowledge of The Holy Scripture).

- 5 laws address issues and prohibitions related to the sacrament of marriage (Requiring communion for couples on the day of their wedding; Prohibiting

marriage to non-Christians; Forbidding arranged marriages of children and infants; Banning “side-to-side” marriages where couples are married in separate churches).

- 1 general law (Prohibition of the performance of church rituals, including weddings outside of the church).

- 2 law, which its full expressive depth and interiority, serves to eradicate the sin of Sodom (both homosexuality and perversions of any lustful activities and desires) – “Sin that angers the God the most”

The hierarch convening the council, with such a laws, not only tries to establish church order and remove unworthy clergy from the priesthood (which is often understood as the sole purpose of the “*Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree*”), but also to organize and regulate the small-scale Church – the family, and its foundation, the sacred ritual of Marriage. At the same time, the Decree strictly legislates for these two pillars of the sovereignty, guarding spiritual values against their main threat – Sodomite sin (both homosexuality and perversions of any lustful activities and desires).

It is obvious, that the ruler who is altogether spiritual teacher of the nation and, as an individual, “The Image and The Likeness of God” – becomes a spiritual “Image and Likeness” of the Saviors soteriological, healing activity towards man.

It should also be said that the idea of a sacred political hierarch and the true portrait of the king are clearly visible in the Georgian tradition of Coronation. According to which the coronation rite is to be performed during one day and night, within vespers and matins prayers. Before the vespers prayer, the Archbishop and clergy, having arrived at the royal palace, will place hierarchal Crown, Scepter, Sakkos and Mantle on a Paten. These royal items are then placed on the the Sanctuary on the Holy Table. The royal candidate must stay awake throughout the night. When the time for the morning liturgical service comes, the following is said: “They should knock three times on the pole and gather in the church” [4. 61].

Interestingly, the coronation rule does not involve ringing the church bells but is limited to three strikes on pole. This tradition deeply rooted in asceticism that evokes the crucifixion of the Savior and the sound of hammer blows on the cross.

During the ceremonial liturgy, after the reading of the Gospel, the candidate, dressed in a Sakkos, kneels three times before the gates of sanctuary. He is then led to the altar to the Holy Table by the Catholicoses of Abkhazia and Ishkhani. After each Archbishop places an omophorion on the head of the kneeling candidate, the rite of coronation is performed along with the service of Righteous and with Eucharist, during which the newly anointed king receives communion in the altar after the Patriarch and before the Priests.

“*Kalmasoba*” by Ioane Batonishvili

Following the annexation of Georgia by the Russian Empire, from the late 18th century to the early 19th century, Georgia experienced significant social and economic changes. This period of transformation evidently had a corresponding impact on the country’s cultural and intellectual condition. A vivid example of this

is “*Kalmasoba*” by Ioane Batonishvili (1768–1830), which is recognized as the first Georgian Enlightenment era’s type of text. The great Georgian theologian Ioane Khelashvili (1778–1837) appears as its lyrical protagonist. The work is, in a sense, written in the style of Latin *Suasoriae*, presenting an imaginary, fictional journey and a conversation involving a real historical figure.

It should be noted, that the author, who was well-educated in the French Enlightenment (characterized by the rise of empiricism, the promotion of freedom, and skepticism towards religious institutions as a counterbalance to accumulating encyclopedic knowledge), adopted from it only its methodological approach rather than its religious perspectives. This meant advocating for the right to access knowledge and, more broadly, the right to education.

This is clearly seen in the early dialogues of the narrative, where the main character is described as a figure who is “doer according to words of the Gospels” [1, 4], while when asked about meaning being disciple of Voltaire, he immediately replies: “The lovelessness of God and the ruthlessness of men” [1, 5].

The work, which spreads and evaluates the ideology of three main laws (natural law, divine law, and civil law), essentially seeks to introduce Europeanism into the Georgian cultural sphere and create first Enlightenment-style of encyclopedia. This encyclopedia was intended to offer readers deep knowledge across all scientific fields of the time. The text addresses theology, philosophy, psychology, ethics, logic, jurisprudence, mythology, linguistics, poetics, rhetoric, grammar, history, architecture, geography, anthropology, metallurgy, mathematics, physics, astronomy, climatology, anatomy, zoology, medicine, and military strategy.

Alongside its attempt to provide readers with systematic information about all of these above-mentioned scientific disciplines, the core value of the work lies in its philosophical approach. Firstly, the author aims to make knowledge accessible through simple, humorous dialogues. He achieves this by synthesizing the Socratic method with the didactic tone of the Gospels, emphasizing the principles of thought and worldview upon which he aims to build a unique Georgian Enlightenment.

To understand this better, it is essential to construct a brief political-theological overview of “*Kalmasoba*” as a less-explored work in this regard. This will allow us to uncover the ideological foundations shaping Georgian philosophical thought as Christian philosophy in the early 19th century. Unlike the fictional and publicistic prose of the time (such as Jean-Jacques Rousseau’s *Émile, or Treatise On Education*; Voltaire’s *Candide*; Denis Diderot’s *Rameau’s Nephew*, and others), this exceptional Georgian text not only critiques and exposes country’s downward reality and spiritual diseases, but also outlines pathways for renewal, vividly revealing the Georgian spirit and Orthodox worldview.

Ioane Batonishvili, as an author, who believes that the foundation of statehood is in philosophical approach and sovereignty must mean governance based

on knowledge and education, sends his main character – Protodeacon Ioane Khelashvili on a journey across the whole country to replenish the monastery’s supplies of bread and wine.

We have to clarify that politics (πολιτικά) is understood in the sense of the Greek city-state and like the Church (ἐκκλησία), both necessarily has to be based on collectivity and unity. Since that some of the fundamental ideas of the Enlightenment contradict Orthodox teachings and the ideology of Deism denies a personal relationship between man and God, Ioane Batonishvili, in contrast, seeks to build his Enlightenment on the early-mentioned diptych of “man and God”. When the protagonist greets Zuraba, his then companion on the journey, he greets him with the blessing of Matins prayers (especially, when reader gets the blessing words from the Priest after reading the Epistles): “Peace be unto Thee!” and gest response: “And to Thy Spirit”. After such a greeting, when Ioane asks about Zuraba’s intentions and the path the Lord has set for him, Zuraba replies that he is going: “Wherever to educate my children,” to which Ioane immediately responds: “Therefore, you are going to *Kalmasoba!*” (as noted earlier, the medieval Georgian technical term, meaning going outside of the Monastery to collect and replenish the supply of bread and wine) [1, 1].

In general, for fictional and publicistic literature the opening words and the plot often hold special importance, offering insight into the writer’s main ideas. Often, these openings contain the solutions to many issues of the plot itself. For Ioane Batonishvili, “raising children”—the citizens of the country—is equivalent to journey for “*Kalmasoba*”, even though Ioane’s immediate task is to deliver bread and wine to his specific Monastery. So, Naturally, the question arises: how can a one Liturgical Service performed in a single monastery equate to the “education of children” or society as a whole? It is no coincidence that, in his search for bread and wine, Ioane traverses the entire country, nor is it an accidental that the Proskomedia and Eucharist, celebrated in Christ’s Church, are universal. Because during the Great Entrance accompanied with the Cherubimic hymn (when taking Chalice and Paten out of the Sanctuary), not only the authorities and Orthodox Christians of the country are mentioned collectively, but also who have been died within Christian faith. Thus, the true political theology is founded on pillars that guarantee unity from God’s perspective—a paradisiacal vision in which the living and the dead are called for eternal life and *Theosis*, where the visible and invisible are united as one.

It is no coincidence that “*Kalmasoba*” echoes the architectonics of the “*Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree*”. It begins with the sermon on creation of the world and purpose of the humanity and rather than with naming secular laws, continues with a spiritual canon, and reminds its readers of the Creed, the Seven Sacraments of the Church (Baptism, Chrismation, Confession, Eucharist, Marriage, Ordination and Oil Anointing), provides full information about main fasting days of the Church

calendar and, notably, the praising speech delivered by Ioane upon the return of the king from his military deeds imitates and even mirrors the part of the “*Ruis-Urbnisi Legal Decree*” text, where Arsen Ikaltoeli praises King David IV the Builder.

The relationship between the Enlightenment and Christianity, and how political theology is addressed in this work, is evident in a comment made to Ioane Khelashvili who preaches and spreads the knowledge: “We cannot gather bread and wine if you preach everywhere you go” [1, 10]. Or in trembling Ioane’s words when he flees from the village in danger, not remembering his desires and goals and hides in despair. Angry and regretful, he criticizes himself: “I preferred the protection of my soul and body to replenish a single store-room of wheat (i.e., collecting wheat for bread)” [1, 17].

That is, for the protagonist (and for the author himself), replenishing the one specific monastery’s wheat supply is more important than educating the entire nation, because nothing should hinder the service of the Divine Liturgy. To the question, “Why did God create man?” the author, through Ioane, answers: “To follow God’s law, to be righteous, to learn good deeds in this world, and to glorify His name” [1, 13]. And unlike Europe, where “there is such an air that it soon cools a man’s heart” [1, 30], in response to the fundamental question of a nation’s life, “What is philosophy?” Ioane quickly replies: “Philosophy is likeness of God” [1, 71], and the Kingdom of God, as we learned, is within the hearts of men (Luke 17:21).

Conclusion

King David IV the Builder, who convened the Ruis-Urbnisi Church Council in medieval Georgia, put an end to unworthy clergy and improper marriages, resolving issues related to the Church and marriage (small-scale Church). By founding the Academy of Gelati, he managed to synthesize Athens and Jerusalem, where, following the model of the Mangana Academy, the Trivium-Quadrivium system was used for teaching. Similarly, Ioane Batonishvili, the Nobleman, created encyclopedic work and entrusted the Clerical protagonist – Protodeacon with the mission of enlightening the peasantry.

Thus, Georgian political theology is Christocentric, and Georgian Enlightenment – Liturgical.

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